

PREPRINT

Technical Note

Social Network Analysis of Remote Sensing Projects in H2020 with R Zsolt Tóth¹

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Abstract

The study analysed H2020 projects in the remote sensing using SNA methods. It was performed using R. Based on the data set from CORDIS, an adjacency matrix was constructed and used to plot the network of project participants. Various network indicators were then calculated. In search of notable distributions in network research several statistical methods (maximum likelihood, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, moments, bootstrapping) were used to perform a goodness-of-fit analysis on the frequencies of the degrees, to verify randomness or scale-freedom. The small-world nature was also investigated. The results show that the distribution of the degrees of project participants reflects multiple effects.

remote sensing / project / SNA / H2020 / R

Code (R) and results

Setting of working directory

```
setwd("<working directory>")
```

Libraries

```
library(RSQLite)
library(igraph)
library(vcd)
library(powerLaw)
library(fitdistrplus)
```

Creating a formal class to SQLite Connections

```
projects <- dbConnect(RSQLite::SQLite(), "<path>")
```

Creating data frame

```
h2020_participations <- dbGetQuery(projects,
  "SELECT * FROM v_2020_remote_sensing_project_participants")
```

Number of the occurrences of projects

```
proj_occur <- table(h2020_participations$projectID)
proj_length <- length(proj_occur)
proj_numlist <- vector(mode='list', length=proj_length)
l <- 1
for(l in 1:proj_length){
  proj_numlist [l] <- proj_occur[l]
}
```

Creating project participants' network

```
i <- 0
```

```

j <- 0
k <- c()
i_v <- c()
j_v <- c()
z <- c()
for (z in 1:proj_length){
  z_num <- as.numeric(proj_numlist[z])
  j <- j + z_num
  i <- j - z_num + 1
  if(proj_occur[z]!=1){ #1-member projects elimination
    proj_comb <- t(combn(i:j,2))
    proj_comb_length <- length(proj_comb[,1])
    for (pc in 1:proj_comb_length){
      row1 <- proj_comb[pc,1]
      row2 <- proj_comb[pc,2]
      i_v <- append(i_v, h2020_participations[row1, 18])
      j_v <- append(j_v, h2020_participations[row2, 18])
    }
  }
}
}

```

Creating the graph

```

el <- list(i = i_v, j = j_v)
el2 <- matrix(unlist(el), nrow = length(i_v), ncol = 2)
graph_1 <- graph_from_edgelist(el2, directed = FALSE)

```

Creating the adjacency matrix

```

matrix_adj <- as_adjacency_matrix(graph_1,
  type = "both",
  attr = NULL,
  edges = FALSE,
  names = TRUE,
  sparse = T
)

```

Creating an optimal graph for igraph

```

net <- graph_from_adjacency_matrix(
  matrix_adj,
  mode = "min",
  weighted = NULL,
  diag = TRUE,
  add.colnames = NULL,
  add.rownames = NA
)

```

Plot network

```

V(net)$size <- 4
V(net)$frame.color <- "white"
V(net)$color <- "red"
V(net)$label <- ""
E(net)$arrow.mode <- 0
plot(net)

```

Output:

Network measures

```
edge_density(net, loops = F)
transitivity(net, type = "global")
diameter(net, directed = F)
deg <- degree(net, mode = "all")
hist(deg,
  freq = TRUE,
  xlim = range(deg),
  ylim = NULL,
  xlab = "Degree",
  ylab = "Frequency",
  main=""
)
```

Output:

```
[1] 0.03256541
[1] 0.6141441
[1] 5
```


1-5th actors (rcn) by betweenness

```
net.between <- betweenness(net, directed=F, weights=NA)
net.between.sort <- sort(net.between, decreasing = TRUE)
net.between.sort[1:5]
```

Output:

```
1905609 1919568 1909988 1905675 1905579
29935.07 22338.78 15266.06 12484.88 10200.24
```

Clusters

```
ceb <- cluster_edge_betweenness(net, directed = FALSE)
length(ceb)
plot(ceb, net, vertex.size=3, vertex.label=NA)
c_vec <- 1:length(ceb)
for (x in 1:length(ceb)){
  c_vec[x] <- length(unlist(ceb[x]))
}
c_vec
max(c_vec)
```

Output:

```
[1] 62
[1] 8 64 73 26 51 22 27 51 9 6 6 22 25 18 4 1 1 19 11 9 6 1 5 2 9 2
5 9 1 1 13 6 1 4 15 9 3 3
[39] 2 2 4 15 6 9 8 4 5 3 2 3 2 2 11 8 2 2 2 3 7 1 7 2
[1] 73
```


Goodness of fit analysis of Poisson distribution

```
gf_poisson_deg <- goodfit(deg, type = "poisson", method = "ML")
summary(gf_poisson_deg)
rootogram(gf_poisson_deg, xlab = "Degress", ylab = "SQRT(frequencies)")
unlist(gf_poisson_deg$par)
gf_poisson_deg$fitted
gf_poisson_deg$observed
gf_poisson_deg$count
gf_poisson_deg$type
gf_poisson_deg$method
gf_poisson_deg$df
```

```
gf_poisson_deg$par
qchisq(p = 0.95, df = gf_poisson_deg$df)
```

Output (partial):

```
Goodness-of-fit test for poisson distribution
      X^2 df P(>X^2)
Likelihood Ratio 8848.061 76 0
```



```
> gf_poisson_deg$df
[1] 76
> gf_poisson_deg$par
$lambda
[1] 21.46061

> qchisq(p = 0.95, df = gf_poisson_deg$df)
[1] 97.35097
```

Power distribution goodness of fit analysis

```
power.law.fit(deg, force.continuous = F, implementation = "plfit")
```

Output:

```
$continuous
[1] FALSE
$alpha
[1] 3.551786
$xmin
[1] 31
$logLik
[1] -627.4876
$KS.stat
[1] 0.0677965
$KS.p
[1] 0.4459232
```

Power distribution goodness of fit analysis 2

```
m_pl <- displ$new(deg)
est <- estimate_xmin(m_pl)
est
m_pl$setXmin(est)
bs <- bootstrap(m_pl, no_of_sims = 500, threads = 2)
plot(bs, trim = 0.1)
bs_p <- bootstrap_p(m_pl, no_of_sims = 500, threads = 2)
bs_p
bs_p$x
plot(bs_p, trim = 0.1)
```

bs_p\$bootstraps

Output (partial):

```
$gof  
[1] 0.06779649  
$xmin  
[1] 31  
$pars  
[1] 3.551786  
$ntail  
[1] 162  
$distance  
[1] "ks"  
attr(,"class")  
[1] "estimate_xmin"
```



```
$p  
[1] 0.016  
$gof  
[1] 0.06779649  
$sim_time  
[1] 0.9922468
```


Skewness and kurtosis

```
plotdist(deg, histo = T, demp = T, discrete = T)
```

```
descdist(deg, boot = 1000)
```

```
descdist(deg, discrete = T, boot = 1000)
```

Output:

summary statistics

```
min: 1 max: 237
```

```
median: 17
```

```
mean: 21.46061
```

```
estimated sd: 22.23212
```

estimated skewness: 3.724382
estimated kurtosis: 26.36904

Cullen and Frey graph

min: 1 max: 237
median: 17
mean: 21.46061
estimated sd: 22.23212
estimated skewness: 3.724382
estimated kurtosis: 26.36904

Cullen and Frey graph

Sources

Zsolt Tóth. (2022). Dataset of H2020 projects related to remote sensing.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101380>

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